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Effective, Real-time Ultrasound Video Communications Over HSPA Networks Using Despeckle Filtering

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Abstract— The paper presents an effective video communications system that uses despeckle filtering prior to real-time transmission. The system is demonstrated using an open-source mHealth video communication framework for real-time transmission over 3.5G HSPA wireless networks. Unlike communications with the original clinical ultrasound videos, the use of despeckle filtering provides reconstructions at diagnostically acceptable PSNR levels.

I. INTRODUCTION AND METHODOLOGY

We introduce an effective ultrasound video communications system that is built using open-source technologies that were first introduced in [1]. Here, the promise of the use of despeckle filtering prior to video encoding was recently demonstrated in [2], where the best performing DsFlsmv filter was found to reduce bitrate demands by 39.2% compared to standard H.264/AVC encoding. The current paper extends this prior research by considering the performance of despeckle filtering in real-life scenarios that include wireless ultrasound video transmission.

The open-source telemedicine platform is based on the use of the ffmpeg libraries for pre-processing, the x264 software for H.264/AVC coding, and Videolan project (VLC) to stream the encoded video. Experiments were performed over widely deployed 3.5G HSPA wireless infrastructure, with typical upload data rates between 1 Mbps – 1.2 Mbps. The data set consisted of five atherosclerotic plaque ultrasound videos with a spatial video resolution 560x416 at 25 frames per second (fps). The videos were encoded at 768 kbps and 1024 kbps and the results depict average values of 5 transmissions.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 presents ultrasound video quality results that compare the encoded videos with the reconstructed, decoded videos following transmission via the 3.5G HSPA channel. Here, we consider the use of three despeckle filters: DsFlsmv, DsHhmedian, and DsFsrاد (see [2] for filter definitions).

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Fig. 1. Real-time ultrasound video communications using despeckle filtering. PSNR scores for the whole dataset (5 videos): (a) Encoded videos @768kbps, (b) Decoded videos @768 kbps (following transmission), (c) Encoded videos @1024 kbps, (d) Decoded videos @1024 kbps (following transmission).

From the results, it is clear that for most videos, the use of despeckle filtering results in better-quality video decodings. Furthermore, similar to the results in [2], the DsFlsmv gave the best performance. Moreover, we observe the same trend for wireless transmission, as depicted in Figs. 1(b) and 1(d). The DsFlsmv filter achieves the best PSNR ratings followed by DsHhmedian and DsFsrاد.

Most importantly, video quality assessment for the DsFlsmv remains consistently higher than the diagnostically acceptable threshold of 35dB defined in [3], for both 768 kbps and 1024 kbps encodings. This is not the case for the rival despeckle filters and original videos encoded at 768 kbps. At 1024 kbps, all methods attain diagnostically acceptable PSNR ratings (except an outlier single video) which are verified by the relevant medical expert.

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